

Religious cults in Romania under the attention of the Securitate forces during the communist period

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Religious cults in Romania under security scrutiny during the communist period

Abstract:

The article "*Religious Cults in Romania under the Attention of the Securitate during the Communist Period*" examines how the communist regime in Romania supervised and controlled the activities of religious cults. In the context of the atheistic ideology promoted by the state, the Securitate considered religion as a potential threat to political stability and attempted to marginalize it. The Romanian Orthodox Church, although in the majority, was strictly monitored and its leaders were forced to cooperate with the authorities to avoid persecution. At the same time, minority cults, such as Catholics, Baptists, Adventists, Pentecostals, Jehovah's Witnesses and other religious cults, were targeted with even more severe control and intimidation measures due to fear of external influences.

Keywords: security, communism, religion, surveillance, repression.

Introduction

During the communist era, the Securitate, the secret service of the Socialist Republic of Romania, closely monitored and controlled the activities of religious cults, considering them a potential threat to the regime. The communist regime promoted an atheist ideology and attempted to marginalize the role of religion in society. In this context, the Securitate developed complex strategies to monitor and control the various religious denominations in Romania, from the Romanian Orthodox Church to minority cults, such as Catholics, Baptists, Evangelical Christians, Adventists, Pentecostals, Jehovah's Witnesses and other recognized cults or unrecognized by law.

The Romanian Orthodox Church, although a majority and seemingly privileged one, was subject to strict surveillance to ensure the loyalty of its leaders to the regime. At the same time, church leaders were often forced to collaborate with the communist authorities to maintain their positions and avoid direct persecution. Minority cults, on the other hand, were given even greater attention, being considered more susceptible to external influences and therefore more dangerous to the regime.

The Securitate used various methods to control religious cults, including the infiltration of informants, surveillance of religious leaders and believers, pressure, and blackmail. Some religious leaders were arrested, intimidated, or even eliminated for refusing to comply with Communist Party directives. At the same time, the Communist authorities promoted intense propaganda to discredit religion, presenting it as an obstacle to socialist progress.

Cults were severely restricted in their public and private activities. The number of theological seminaries was limited, independent religious publications were banned, and religious education was removed from schools. Religious buildings were also monitored and, in many cases, confiscated or demolished under various pretexts.

On the other hand, despite the repression, religious cults continued to play an important role in the spiritual life of many Romanians. Religious practices continued underground, and believers found ingenious ways to keep their faith alive. This demonstrated the spiritual resilience of the population in the face of political oppression.

The interaction between religious cults and the Securitate reflects the complexity of the relations between the state and religion in a totalitarian regime. Although the communist regime managed to partially undermine and control religious institutions, it could not completely eliminate the influence of religion from public and private life. The study of this period reveals not only the repressive methods of the communist state, but also the capacity for adaptation and resistance of religious communities.

1. The principles of communist ideology regarding religion

Communist ideology, based on the works of Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels, adopts a materialist worldview in which religion is seen as an obstacle to social and political progress. According to this perspective, religion is considered "the opium of the people," a famous phrase by Marx that suggests that religion serves as a mechanism for illusory relief from human suffering, replacing revolutionary action with passivity. In essence, communist ideology sees religion as a power structure that perpetuates inequalities and class oppression¹.

Communist regimes, inspired by Marxist-Leninist ideology, sought to build a secularized society in which the state controlled all aspects of social life, including religion. This approach was embodied in various policies and measures designed to undermine and control the influence of religion in society.

A central tenet of communist ideology is dialectical materialism, which rejects any form of mysticism and claims that reality is exclusively material. Dialectical materialism asserts that all phenomena, including social and historical ones, are the result of the interaction of material forces. From this perspective, religion, being based on belief in supernatural entities, is viewed as an "enemy of science, a brake on scientific progress"².

Lenin, one of the main theorists of communism, developed Marxist ideas on religion, emphasizing the need to fight against religious influence. Lenin considered religion to be a tool of the bourgeoisie to keep the proletariat in a state of submission and passivity. He argued that in order to achieve a classless society, it was essential to eliminate religion from public and private life. To this end, the Communist Party was to promote scientific atheism and educate the population in the spirit of dialectical materialism³.

Communist regimes implemented state policies to discourage religious practices and promote atheism. These policies ranged from overt persecution and violence against religious leaders and believers to more subtle strategies of control and co-optation of religious institutions. For example, in the Soviet Union, churches were closed, religious property was confiscated, and religious leaders were arrested or executed. In parallel, the regime promoted intense atheist propaganda through schools, the media, and other cultural institutions⁴.

In communist Romania, the regime adopted a mixed strategy towards religion, alternating periods of harsh reprisals with periods of cooptation and collaboration. After the establishment of the communist regime in 1947, the state took control of religious denominations, subordinating them to state authorities. The Romanian Orthodox Church, for example, was forced to collaborate with the regime, accepting state intervention in the internal affairs of the church, including the appointment of clergy.

¹Nicolae Frigioiu, *European Social Democracy in the 20th Century*, Bucharest, Institute of Social Theory Publishing House, 1998, p. 32.

²Sergey Ivanovich Kovalev, *The Atheist's Guide*, Bucharest, Politica Publishing House, 1962, p. 377.

³*Ibid.*, p. 510.

⁴*Ibid.*, pp. 528-529.

The Romanian communist regime established the Department of Cults, a government agency designed to supervise and control religious activities. Through this department, the state monitored sermons, charitable activities, and any other religious manifestations, ensuring that they did not contradict state policy. In parallel, the regime carried out intense atheist propaganda, especially through the educational system, where students were taught about the superiority of scientific materialism and the futility of religion⁵.

Another aspect of communist policy towards religion was the attempt to create state religious organizations that were completely subordinate to the authorities. In the Soviet Union, for example, the regime attempted to establish a state-controlled Soviet Orthodox Church. Organizations such as the League of Militant Atheists were also established to promote atheism and combat religious influence.

In China, under Mao Zedong, the policy towards religion was even more extreme. During the Cultural Revolution, all forms of religion were declared enemies of the people, and religious practitioners were brutally persecuted. Temples, churches, mosques, and other places of worship were destroyed, and religious activities were banned.

Similarly, in other communist countries in Eastern Europe, the regimes adopted harsh policies toward religion, combining direct repression with propaganda and re-education efforts. In Poland, where the Catholic Church had significant influence, the communist regime encountered strong opposition from the clergy and lay believers, leading to open conflicts and persistent resistance against policies of forced secularization⁶.

Up to this point we can say that the principles of communist ideology regarding religion are based on dialectical materialism and the rejection of any form of supernatural belief. Communist regimes perceived religion as an obstacle to revolutionary progress and implemented various policies to undermine and control the influence of religion in society. These policies included direct persecution, institutional control, and atheist propaganda, all aimed at eliminating religion as a social factor and promoting a secularized and materialistic society. Although the degree of success of these policies varied from country to country, the impact on religious cults was profound and lasting, leaving deep traces in their structure and functioning.

2. Institutionalization of the communist regime

The institutionalization of the communist regime in Romania was a complex and gradual process, which involved major transformations in the political, economic and social structure of the country. This process began immediately after World War II and was marked by the massive intervention of the Soviet Union, which played a crucial role in the installation and consolidation of the communist regime.

After the war, Romania came under the influence of the Soviet Union, which imposed a pro-communist government. In 1945, the Romanian Communist Party (PCR) began to gain control of the government, initially through a series of alliances with other political parties. These alliances were short-lived, however, as the PCR used tactics of intimidation and elimination of political opposition to take full control. Through political and administrative measures, the PCR gradually managed to eliminate non-communist parties, culminating in the dissolution of the National Peasant Party and the National Liberal Party in 1947⁷.

A key step in the institutionalization of the communist regime was the forced abdication of King Michael I on December 30, 1947, and the proclamation of the Romanian

⁵Adrian Nicolae Petcu, George Enache, Denisa Budeancă, *Ministry/Department of Cults*, in vol. *Securitatea (1948-1989): Monograph*, Florian Banu, Liviu Țăranu (coord.), vol. I, Târgoviște, Cetatea de Scaun, 2016, p. 417.

⁶Susan Muaddi Darraj, *The Collapse of the Soviet Union*, New York, Chelsea House Publishers, 2010, p. 12.

⁷Gheorghe Onișoru, *Stalin and the Russian people ...: democracy and dictatorship in the contemporary world*, vol. II, Bucharest, Corint, 2021, p. 233.

People's Republic. This marked the end of the monarchy and the beginning of a totalitarian regime, in which power was concentrated in the hands of the Romanian Communist Party. In the immediate aftermath, the new regime began to implement policies of nationalization and collectivization, radically transforming the economy and property structure of Romania⁸.

The nationalization of major industries, banks, and natural resources was one of the first major measures of the communist regime. This was accomplished through a series of decrees and laws adopted starting in 1948, which transferred private property to state ownership. This process was accompanied by expropriations and confiscations, particularly affecting the economic and political elites of the old regime. Nationalization allowed the state to completely control the economy, eliminating the private sector and consolidating the economic base of the communist regime.

Another crucial aspect of the institutionalization of the communist regime was the collectivization of agriculture. This began in 1949 and continued until the early 1960s. The aim of collectivization was to transform traditional agriculture, based on the private property of small farmers, into a system of collective farms and state-owned agricultural cooperatives. The collectivization process was extremely painful and met with considerable resistance from the peasants, who were forced to give up their lands. The methods used by the regime to implement collectivization included intimidation, violence, and mass arrests. Collectivization led to profound changes in the social structure of the Romanian village, abolishing private property and subordinating agriculture to centralized planning.

The institutionalization of the communist regime also involved a profound restructuring of the state apparatus. The PCR centralized political and administrative power, eliminating any form of opposition and establishing strict control over all aspects of public and private life. In this regard, the Securitate, the secret police service, played a crucial role. Established in 1948, the Securitate quickly became an instrument of repression and social control, using extensive surveillance, arrests and torture to eliminate any threat to the regime⁹.

Culturally and ideologically, the communist regime initiated a massive propaganda and re-education campaign, designed to transform the mentality of the population and consolidate Marxist-Leninist ideology. The media, the educational system, and cultural institutions were subordinated to the party and used to promote communist values and denigrate old traditions and institutions. Censorship was strict, and any form of dissent or criticism of the regime was severely punished.

Social transformations were also profound. The communist regime promoted a forced equalization of society, eliminating old hierarchies and privileges. Through policies of redistribution of resources and free access to education and health, the state attempted to create a classless society, although in practice new forms of inequality and privilege emerged, linked to loyalty to the party and to positions held in the state apparatus.

On the international stage, Romania became a staunch ally of the Soviet Union, integrating into the communist bloc and adopting policies dictated by Moscow. This included participation in Soviet-controlled international organizations. Although Romania experienced some moments of relative autonomy, especially under Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej and Nicolae Ceaușescu, Soviet influence remained predominant in the early years of the communist regime.

An important element of the institutionalization of the communist regime was the creation of a personality cult around the party leaders. Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej and, later,

⁸Ion Calafeteanu (coord.), *The Romanian Revolution of December 1989. Documents*, Cluj-Napoca, Military Publishing House, 2009, p. 40.

⁹Lavinia Betea, *Maurer and the world of yesterday. Testimonies about the Stalinization of Romania*, Arad, "Ioan Slavici" Publishing House, 1995, p. 29.

Nicolae Ceaușescu were presented as great leaders and liberators of the nation, in the style of Soviet leaders such as Stalin. This personality cult was cultivated through propaganda and official symbols, consolidating the leaders' authority and legitimizing the communist regime¹⁰.

In conclusion, the institutionalization of the communist regime in Romania was a complex and multidimensional process, which involved fundamental changes in the political, economic and social structure of the country. Through a combination of repression, centralized control and ideological propaganda, the PCR managed to impose a totalitarian regime that radically transformed Romanian society. Although these changes were presented as modernization and social progress, in reality they brought suffering and deprivation to the majority of the population, subordinating all aspects of life to the interests of the communist state.

3. State policy towards cults and churches

The communist state's policy towards cults and churches was complex and multifaceted, evolving from direct and brutal repression to more subtle strategies of control and co-optation. After the establishment of the communist regime in Romania, the relationship between the state and churches was defined by the main objective of the Romanian Communist Party (PCR): the complete subordination of all social institutions, including religious ones, in order to consolidate the party's power and promote Marxist-Leninist ideology.

Immediately after taking power, the communist regime launched an aggressive campaign to repress religious cults. This was manifested in the arrest and sentencing of many religious leaders, the confiscation of church property, and the closure of religious educational institutions. The Securitate, the regime's new secret police, played a central role in these actions, overseeing religious activities and infiltrating agents into church structures to control and manipulate religious communities¹¹.

Despite the repression, the communist regime quickly realized that the complete elimination of religion was unrealistic and that a significant part of the population remained deeply religious. As a result, state policy began to adapt, aiming to co-opt the churches and transform them into instruments of the state. The Romanian Orthodox Church (ROC), the largest and most influential church in the country, became a main target of this strategy. The state offered the ROC a limited degree of autonomy in exchange for cooperation and loyalty to the regime. In this context, some Orthodox leaders were forced to collaborate with the communist authorities to maintain the functioning of the church and avoid reprisals.

A crucial instrument in the state's control over religious communities was the Department of Cults, established in 1949.¹² This department was tasked with monitoring and regulating all aspects of religious activities, from the appointment of clergy and local leaders¹³ to the approval of construction projects for places of worship. It even recommended, in some areas, the composition of local governing bodies¹⁴. The Department of Cults worked closely with the Securitate to supervise religious activities and identify any form of opposition or subversive activity¹⁵.

¹⁰S. Berstein, P. Milza, *History of Europe*, vol. V, Iași, European Institute Publishing House, 1998, p. 20.

¹¹Marius Oprea, *The Banality of Evil. A History of the Securitate in Documents (1949-1989)*, Iași, Polirom Publishing House, 2002, pp. 463-466.

¹²Adrian Nicolae Petcu, George Enache, Denisa Budeancă, *op. cit.* p. 420.

¹³Central National Historical Archives (ANIC), Ministry of Religions and Arts fund, file 109/1954, f. 53. In the mentioned file there are many addresses submitted by the Seventh-day Adventist Church to the Ministry of Religions and which contain lists of those elected to the leadership of local churches.

¹⁴*Ibid.*, p. 146.

¹⁵Archives of the National Council for the Study of Security Archives (ACNSAS), Documentary collection, file 014720, vol. 3, f. 73.

The regime also used intense propaganda to undermine the influence of religion. The educational system was reformed to exclude any form of religious education, replacing it with the teaching of scientific atheism and dialectical materialism. Youth were the main target of this propaganda, with the aim of creating a new generation loyal to communist ideology and skeptical of religious beliefs¹⁶. State propaganda also constantly promoted messages that discredited religions and presented religious leaders as outdated and reactionary¹⁷.

At the same time, the regime resorted to more subtle strategies to weaken the internal structure of the churches and create divisions among the faithful. This included promoting clerics loyal to the regime to leadership positions and using them to influence the doctrinal direction and activities of the churches. Some smaller denominations, which did not have the same degree of influence as the BOR, were subjected to even greater pressure, often being forced to cease their activities or operate underground¹⁸.

Another important aspect of the state's policy towards religions was the attempt to use churches to legitimize the regime both domestically and internationally. The participation of religious leaders in state events and international visits was orchestrated to create an image of harmony and cooperation between the state and the church¹⁹. In return, religious leaders received certain concessions, such as permission to open new places of worship or to carry out limited charitable activities, as long as these did not conflict with the interests of the regime²⁰.

During Nicolae Ceaușescu's reign, the policy towards religions experienced certain nuances. Although direct repression continued, Ceaușescu attempted to adopt a more nationalist stance and use churches as instruments of his policy of independence from the Soviet Union. In this context, relations with some churches became more complex, and certain concessions were made to maintain a delicate balance between control and co-optation.

However, the state policy remained essentially one of strict subordination and control. Even during periods of apparent openness, any religious manifestation that could be interpreted as a form of political opposition was harshly repressed. A notable example is the case of Father Gheorghe Calciu-Dumitreasa²¹, who was arrested and convicted for his sermons critical of the regime.

After the 1989 revolution and the fall of the communist regime, many details of the state's repressive and controlling policies towards cults and churches were revealed. Securitate documents and survivor testimonies revealed²² the extent of surveillance and infiltration among religious communities. It also became evident that, despite persecution, religion continued to play an important role in the lives of many Romanians, and passive and active resistance contributed to the maintenance of religious identity²³.

In conclusion, the communist state's policy towards cults and churches was characterized by a mixture of repression, control and co-optation. The main goal was the complete subordination of religious institutions to serve the interests of the party and promote

¹⁶ANIC, file 96/1960, pp. 36-37.

¹⁷*Ibid*

¹⁸A CNSAS, Documentary collection, file 004054, vol. 3, f. 5. The activity of the Reformed Adventists (an officially unrecognized cult) is broken up, but the active members act illegally.

¹⁹A CNSAS, Information fund, file 4973 /III Annex, pp. 402 – 404.

²⁰Nicolae Baci, *The Collapse of the Soviet Empire, The Great Betrayal*, Bucharest, Politica Document, 1991, p. 24.

²¹<https://gheorghecalciu.ro/viata-parintelui-gheorghe-calciu/>, accessed on June 7, 2024.

²²See the *Sighet Annals collection* regarding the testimonies of those who were in detention.

²³Cornel Onaca, *Witnesses and Martyrs from Communist Prisons*, Bucharest, Evdokimos Publishing House, 2018, p. 172.

Marxist-Leninist ideology. Although the methods and intensity of repression varied over time, the ultimate objective remained constant: reducing the influence of religion and transforming churches into instruments of the communist state. This policy left deep traces in Romanian society, profoundly affecting the structure and functioning of religious cults²⁴.

4. The structure and functioning of the Security Service

The Securitate, officially known as the General Directorate of State Security (DGSS)²⁵, was one of the most feared and pervasive institutions of the communist regime in Romania. Founded in 1947, at the initiative of the communist government, the Securitate had the primary role of protecting the regime from any form of internal and external opposition, using varied and often brutal methods to maintain political and social control. The structure and functioning of the Securitate reflected a complex organization, designed to ensure total surveillance and control over the population²⁶.

In its early days, the Securitate was modelled after the Soviet NKVD, benefiting from the advice and training of Soviet officers. This included adopting tactics of intimidation, repression, and intelligence gathering similar to those used by the Soviet secret services. The Securitate's organization was divided into several departments and sections, each responsible for a specific aspect of national security, from counterintelligence to domestic surveillance of citizens²⁷.

At the top of the hierarchy was the Minister of the Interior, who coordinated the work of the Securitate and was directly responsible to the leaders of the Romanian Communist Party (PCR). Under his leadership, the Securitate was divided into main directorates, each with specific responsibilities. One of the most important directorates was the Counterintelligence Directorate, responsible for preventing foreign espionage and subversive activities. This directorate supervised foreign embassies and diplomatic personnel, as well as Romanian citizens suspected of having links to foreign intelligence services²⁸.

Another essential element in the Securitate structure was the Internal Intelligence Directorate, which was responsible for monitoring and controlling the internal opposition. This was the department responsible for surveillance of individuals suspected of anti-communist activities, including intellectuals, students, workers, and even members of the Romanian Communist Party. The Internal Intelligence Directorate used a vast network of informants, who provided information about the activities and opinions of citizens. These informants were recruited from all strata of society and were often coerced into collaboration through blackmail or other forms of pressure.

To accomplish its mission, the Securitate had a variety of and often brutal methods at its disposal. Arrests, interrogations, and torture were common practices, designed to intimidate and extract information. Political prisoners were often subjected to inhumane conditions in prisons and labour camps, where they were forced to live in conditions of extreme austerity and endure physical and psychological violence. In addition to the use of brute force, the Securitate also developed sophisticated surveillance techniques, including the interception of telephone conversations, the opening of correspondence, and the use of listening devices²⁹.

²⁴Ion Bălan, *The Concentration Camp Regime in Romania, 1945-1946*, Bucharest, Civic Academy Foundation, 2000, p. 72.

²⁵Florian Banu, Raluca Spiridon, *The Predecessors Security*, in vol. *Securitatea (1948-1989): Monograph*, Florian Banu, Liviu Țăranu (coord.), vol. I, Târgoviște, Cetatea de Scaun, 2016, p. 55.

²⁶*Ibid*

²⁷*Ibidem*, p. 77

²⁸*Ibid*

²⁹A CNSAS, Network Fund, file R6838, f. 470. The file contains the order installing listening devices in the home of the Adventist pastor, Crișan Pavel.

Surveillance of the population was pervasive and well-organized. Every neighbourhood and institution had informants who reported on people's activities and conversations. Even churches and other religious institutions were infiltrated, and clergy were closely monitored. This created an atmosphere of fear and suspicion, where people did not trust themselves to express their opinions freely, even in private circles.

In the 1950s and 1960s, the Securitate further consolidated its control over Romanian society. Purges within the PCR and other government institutions were coordinated by the Securitate, eliminating any potential political rival and ensuring loyalty to the party leadership. During these years, the Securitate played a crucial role in suppressing uprisings and protest movements, such as the workers' uprising in the Jiu Valley and the student uprisings in Cluj.

Throughout the 1970s and 1980s, under Nicolae Ceaușescu, the Securitate became even more sophisticated, expanding its methods of surveillance and influence. Ceaușescu saw the Securitate as an indispensable tool for maintaining his personal power and began using the institution to monitor even his family members and close collaborators. During this period, the Securitate developed modern surveillance technologies and intensified the use of informants, creating an even more efficient domestic espionage network.

The Securitate was not only a force of repression, but also an economic actor. It controlled numerous businesses and economic organizations, using the funds obtained to finance its operations. The Securitate was also involved in external operations, such as infiltrating the Romanian diaspora and monitoring the activities of dissidents in exile.

An important aspect of the functioning of the Securitate was the cult of secrecy and absolute loyalty. Securitate officers were well-trained and the beneficiaries of a reward system that encouraged loyalty and efficiency. They received higher-than-average salaries, access to rare goods and services, and the opportunity to advance rapidly in their careers. In return, any form of dissent or failure was severely punished, both through disciplinary sanctions and more drastic measures³⁰.

However, despite its power and influence, the Securitate failed to prevent the collapse of the communist regime. The 1989 revolution revealed the limits of this repressive machine. In the face of a large-scale popular uprising and geopolitical changes in Eastern Europe, the Securitate was unable to control the situation. After the fall of Ceaușescu, surviving Securitate archives revealed the extent of the regime's surveillance and brutality.

The Securitate was a central institution of the communist regime in Romania, characterized by a complex structure and an omnipresent and often brutal operation. From internal surveillance of citizens to combating external espionage, the Securitate used a wide range of methods to maintain political and social control. This created a climate of fear and suspicion, undermining citizens' trust and freedom. Although it was a powerful instrument of the communist regime, the Securitate could not prevent its eventual collapse, leaving behind a legacy of suffering and suspicion that has deeply marked post-communist Romanian society.

5. Departments and sections specialized in the control of religion

During the communist regime in Romania, control over religion was a central objective of the Securitate, and this control was achieved through a complex structure of specialized departments and sections. These were designed to monitor, supervise, and influence all aspects of religious life, ensuring that no religious activity threatened the ideological and political hegemony of the Romanian Communist Party (PCR).

³⁰Adam Burakowski , Aleksander Gubrynowicz , Pawel Ukielski , *1989 Autumn of Nations*, Iași, Polirom Publishing House , 2013, p. 17.

One of the most important departments in this regard was the General Directorate of Internal Intelligence (DGII), which had extensive powers in surveillance of the population and in combating any form of internal opposition. Within the DGII, the Section for Religious Issues was directly responsible for monitoring religious activities. This section collected information about religious leaders, practitioners, and any religious manifestation that could be interpreted as subversive or contrary to the interests of the state.

The Religious Affairs Section had sub-sections and task forces that focused on different religious cults and denominations. For example, there were sub-sections dedicated to monitoring the Romanian Orthodox Church, the Roman Catholic Church, Protestant and neo-Protestant churches, and other religious minorities, such as the Mosaic and Muslim communities. Each sub-section had specialized agents who were tasked with infiltrating religious communities, collecting information, and reporting any suspicious activity.

Another key department in the control of religion was the Counterintelligence Directorate, which was responsible for preventing and combating espionage and subversive activities. In the religious context, this directorate focused on identifying and neutralizing any links between religious communities and foreign intelligence agencies. Any contact with international religious entities was closely monitored, and clerics who travelled abroad or received visits from abroad were under strict surveillance³¹.

Technical surveillance was another essential component of religious control, managed by the Technical Directorate of Security. This directorate was responsible for intercepting communications, installing listening devices in places of worship and the residences of religious leaders, and monitoring correspondence. Through these technical means, the Securitate could obtain detailed information about the activities and private discussions of religious leaders and believers.

A significant role was also played by the Department for Cults, an official government institution that worked closely with the Securitate. The Department for Cults was tasked with regulating and supervising the activities of all officially recognized cults in Romania. This included approving the construction of new places of worship, controlling religious education, and monitoring public religious events. In essence, the Department for Cults functioned as a civilian arm of the Securitate, ensuring that all religious activities were in line with state policy.

Another aspect of religious control was the direct infiltration of informants into religious communities. These informants were often members of congregations or even clergy who, either voluntarily or under pressure, provided information about the activities and opinions of believers. The Securitate used various methods to recruit informants, including blackmail, offering material benefits, or promoting them to leadership positions within churches.

In addition to direct surveillance and infiltration, the Securitate also carried out propaganda campaigns designed to discredit religion and promote atheism. This was done through the state-controlled media, where religion was presented as a vestige of the reactionary past and an obstacle to socialist progress. The Securitate ensured that propaganda messages reached all levels of society, including schools, where young people were educated in the spirit of dialectical materialism³².

Direct repression of clergy and believers was another tactic used by the Securitate. Religious leaders who refused to cooperate or who criticized the regime were often arrested, tortured, and sentenced to heavy prison sentences. These measures were intended to intimidate and discourage any form of religious opposition. The most notable cases of

³¹Lucian Boia, *Myths of Romanian Communism*, Bucharest, Nemira Publishing House, 1998, p. 24.

³²Peter Calvocoressi, *World Politics after 1945*, Iași, Alfa Publishing House, 2000, p. 77.

repression were those of Father Gheorghe Calciu-Dumitreasa and Pastor Richard Wurmbrand³³, both of whom were subjected to torture and imprisonment for their opposition to the regime.

In addition to internal control, the Securitate also had an external component, responsible for monitoring the religious activities of the Romanian diaspora and influencing international religious organizations. Securitate agents infiltrated Romanian communities abroad to report on their activities and prevent any form of support for the domestic opposition. They also tried to influence the decisions of international religious organizations in order to present the communist regime in a favourable light.

After the 1989 revolution, the archives of the Securitate were partially opened, revealing the extent and complexity of religious surveillance. The documents show that the Securitate had detailed files on most religious leaders and the activities of religious communities. These files included surveillance reports, transcripts of wiretaps, and briefings from informants³⁴.

In conclusion, the structure and functioning of the Securitate in the control of religion were marked by a complex network of specialized departments and sections, which worked closely together to supervise and control all aspects of religious life in communist Romania. Through a combination of surveillance, infiltration, propaganda, and direct repression, the Securitate managed to impose strict control over religious cults, ensuring that they posed no threat to the communist regime. This system of control had profound effects on religious communities and left lasting traces in post-communist Romanian society.

6. Surveillance and control methods

During the communist regime in Romania, the Securitate developed a complex and pervasive system of surveillance and control over the population, with a particular focus on religion and any potential religious opposition. The methods used by the Securitate were varied and evolved over time, becoming increasingly sophisticated and insidious as the regime consolidated its power and faced new challenges.

The communist regime saw religion as a major obstacle to the imposition of an atheistic and materialistic ideology. Thus, the Securitate was tasked with reducing the influence of religion and repressing any form of religious dissent. Surveillance was the first step in this direction, involving a wide range of techniques and technologies to monitor religious activities and those involved in them.

A central method of surveillance was the use of informants. The Securitate recruited large numbers of informants from among the faithful, clergy, and church personnel. These informants were used to provide detailed information about the activities and opinions of religious leaders, as well as the general atmosphere within religious communities. Informants were recruited through various means, including blackmail, psychological pressure, and material rewards. The recruitment of informants was essential because it allowed communist authorities to obtain information directly from within religious communities, so that they could intervene effectively when they detected signs of dissent³⁵.

Telephone tapping and the opening of correspondence were other essential methods of surveillance used by the Securitate. The telephone and mail were the main means of communication, and the Securitate perfected its interception techniques to monitor conversations and exchanges of letters. Any information obtained through these methods was

³³ Richard Wurmbrand, *With God Underground*, Bucharest, Stephanus Publishing House, 2007. The entire book describes the horrors endured in communist prisons as well as survival under the conditions of detention.

³⁴ In consulting the files at ACNSAS and ANIC, we discovered a lot of information that shows the extent of these activities.

³⁵ Jean Louis Dufour, *International Crises*, Bucharest, Corint Publishing House, 2002, p. 56.

meticulously analysed and used to build files on which repressive measures could be taken. The interceptions were not limited to religious leaders, but also extended to lay people active in religious life, including those suspected of having connections with international religious organizations.

The use of listening technology was another method of surveillance heavily employed by the Securitate. Listening devices were installed in churches, clergymen's homes, and other locations where religious activities were held or where religious leaders met with believers. These devices allowed the Securitate to monitor conversations in real time and intervene quickly if they detected activities considered dangerous or subversive³⁶. In addition, Securitate agents often attended services and other religious events undercover to observe behaviour and report any speech or action that might suggest dissent.

Repression was an integral part of communist control over religion and involved harsh measures against those deemed a threat. This included the arrest and prolonged detention of religious leaders who refused to conform to the regime.

Torture and ill-treatment were common methods of repression used by the Securitate to obtain information and discourage dissent. Political prisoners were subjected to inhumane conditions, and confessions obtained through torture were often used to justify convictions and create an atmosphere of fear. These extreme measures were intended to intimidate not only those directly involved, but also others who might have been tempted to resist the communist regime³⁷.

Propaganda was another tool of control used by the Securitate in cooperation with other state institutions. The mass media available at the time were used to discredit religion and promote atheism. Radio, television programs, and newspaper articles presented religion as a remnant of the reactionary past, in contrast to the progress and modernity promoted by communism. The educational system was reformed to exclude religion and instil the values of dialectical materialism among young people. These propaganda measures were intended to weaken the influence of religion in society and create a new generation loyal to the regime.

Infiltrating church leadership was a subtle but effective strategy. The Securitate managed to place agents in key positions within various churches, influencing decisions and doctrinal direction. These agents were tasked with promoting state interests, monitoring the internal activities of the churches, and reporting any activity deemed suspicious. In addition, collaboration with cooperative religious leaders was encouraged by offering privileges, such as permission to build new places of worship or access to scarce material resources.

Strict control over religious education was also essential. Religious education institutions were under constant surveillance, and the curriculum was regulated to ensure compliance with state ideology. Students and teachers in these institutions were closely monitored, and any deviations from the official line were sanctioned. Through these measures, the regime sought to limit the formation of a new generation of religious leaders who could pose a threat to communist authority.

In conclusion, the methods of surveillance and control of religion by the Securitate during the communist period were varied and sophisticated, combining techniques of monitoring, infiltration, propaganda, and outright repression. These methods had a profound impact on religious life in Romania, limiting religious freedom and undermining the influence of churches. However, despite these draconian measures, religion continued to play an important role in the lives of many Romanians, and the passive and active resistance of religious communities contributed to the maintenance of religious identity and faith in the face of communist repression.

³⁶ ACNSAS, Network Fund, file R6838, p. 470

³⁷ Mikhail Gorbachev, *Memories. My Life Before and After Perestroika*, Bucharest, Litera Publishing House, 2015, p. 32.

Conclusions

In the detailed analysis of how the communist regime in Romania interacted with religious cults and used the Securitate to control and repress religion, a complex picture emerges of a period marked by intense conflicts between state and religion. This interaction was dictated by the ideological objectives of communism, which saw religion as a dangerous adversary that had to be eliminated or at least completely subordinated to the interests of the party.

From the beginning, the communist regime perceived religion as a direct threat to the new social order it was trying to impose. The Marxist-Leninist ideology that underpinned the regime promoted atheism and saw religion as a form of oppression that hindered revolutionary progress. Thus, the elimination of religious influence became a central objective of state policy. This was achieved through a combination of legislative measures, intense propaganda, and direct repression, orchestrated by the Securitate.

The Securitate played a key role in implementing the regime's anti-religious policies. Through an extensive network of informants, undercover agents, and sophisticated surveillance techniques, the Securitate was able to penetrate deeply into church structures and monitor religious activities. Informants became a vital tool for gathering information about religious leaders, believers, and any religious activity that could be interpreted as subversive. Through blackmail, psychological pressure, and material benefits, the Securitate was able to recruit a significant number of informants who provided detailed information about religious life in Romania.

Propaganda was another key tool used by the communist regime to discredit religion and promote atheism. Through the state-controlled media, religion was consistently presented as a vestige of the reactionary past, in contrast to the modernity and progress offered by communism. The educational system was also transformed to exclude religious education and promote dialectical materialism. These propaganda efforts were intended to weaken the influence of religion on the population and create a new generation loyal to communist ideology.

Despite these harsh measures, religion continued to play a significant role in the lives of many Romanians. Churches remained centres of passive resistance, where believers found spiritual solace and a sense of community in the face of communist repression. Religious leaders who refused to collaborate with the regime became symbols of resistance, and their suffering inspired many believers to maintain their faith despite the dangers.

The regime also attempted to manipulate church structures from within, promoting loyal religious leaders and using them to influence the doctrinal and administrative direction of the churches. Collaboration with some religious leaders was achieved by offering material privileges and a certain amount of administrative autonomy, but this always came at the cost of loyalty to the state and constant surveillance. In this context, some religious leaders had to navigate carefully between the demands of the state and the spiritual needs of their congregations.

Direct repression was a major component of the communist regime's control over religion. Religious leaders who openly criticized the regime or refused to comply with its directives were often arrested, tortured, and sentenced to heavy prison sentences. These measures were intended to intimidate and discourage any form of religious opposition. However, such actions also had the opposite effect, strengthening the spiritual and moral resistance of many believers who saw the suffering of their leaders as martyrdom for their faith.

On the international stage, the communist regime in Romania attempted to control and manipulate external perceptions of the religious situation in the country. The Securitate

closely monitored the Romanian diaspora and international religious organizations, trying to prevent any external support for religious dissidents. At the same time, the regime used religious delegations and participation in international events to present a false image of harmony and religious freedom.

After the fall of the communist regime in 1989, the extent of religious surveillance and repression by the Securitate was revealed. Documents and testimonies revealed details of the vast network of informants, torture techniques, and the suffering of religious leaders who refused to comply. Although the communist regime attempted to eliminate the influence of religion, it failed to completely suppress the faith and spirituality of the Romanian people. In conclusion, the relationship between the communist state and religious cults in Romania was one of confrontation and strict control, marked by the use of sophisticated methods of surveillance and brutal reprisals. The Securitate played a central role in implementing anti-religious policies, using a combination of monitoring techniques, infiltration, propaganda and violence to subordinate churches to state interests. Despite these efforts, religion continued to represent a bastion of spiritual resistance, and the legacy of this period remains a complex one, in which the suffering and courage of those who resisted are still recognized and honoured. The communist regime failed to completely eliminate the influence of religion, and after its fall, Romania rediscovered and re-evaluated the fundamental role of religion in its identity and cultural life.

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